

A Scalar Field Model with Three Generations and Mass Hierarchies: Symmetry Breaking and Vacuum Expectation Values

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Abstract

This paper presents a scalar field model with three generations of elementary particles. Using a scalar field incorporating a global $U(3)$ flavor symmetry, we explore symmetry breaking and derive multiple vacuum expectation values (VEVs) that differentiate particle masses across generations. By constructing a potential with quadratic, quartic, and generation-mixing terms, we solve for VEVs under cases with and without mixing terms, revealing the effects on symmetry and mass hierarchies. This approach aims to extend the Standard Model and provide insights into the observed three-generation structure.

1 Introduction

The three-generation structure of elementary particles in the Standard Model (SM) lacks an inherent explanation for the observed mass hierarchy. Proposed here is a scalar field model with three components, representing particle generations, where symmetry breaking and unique VEVs contribute to mass differentiation. Using a $U(3)$ flavor symmetry with mixing terms, this study extends previous scalar field models, offering a fresh approach to understanding particle generation structures.

2 Model with Three Generations

2.1 Scalar Field Components

The scalar field ϕ is extended to three components to represent the three generations of particles:

$$\phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3), \tag{2.1}$$

where each ϕ_i is a complex scalar field corresponding to a generation.

2.2 Symmetry Considerations

We assume that the scalar field transforms under a global $U(3)$ flavor symmetry, allowing symmetry breaking to produce the observed mass hierarchies among particle generations.

3 Constructing the Potential

3.1 General Form of the Potential

The potential $V(\phi)$ is designed to be invariant under $U(3)$ symmetry and includes terms that allow for spontaneous symmetry breaking:

$$V(\phi) = V_{\text{quadratic}} + V_{\text{quartic}} + V_{\text{mixing}}, \quad (3.1)$$

where:

- $V_{\text{quadratic}}$ includes mass terms,
- V_{quartic} includes self-interaction terms, and
- V_{mixing} includes terms that mix different components.

3.2 Explicit Form of the Potential

The potential takes the form:

$$V(\phi) = -\mu^2(\phi^\dagger\phi) + \lambda(\phi^\dagger\phi)^2 + \alpha(\phi^\dagger T\phi), \quad (3.2)$$

where:

- $\mu^2 > 0$ ensures spontaneous symmetry breaking,
- $\lambda > 0$ ensures stability of the potential,
- α controls the strength of mixing between generations, and
- T is a Hermitian matrix introducing generation mixing.

3.3 Specifying the Mixing Matrix

The mixing matrix T is chosen as:

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & t_{12} & t_{13} \\ t_{12} & 0 & t_{23} \\ t_{13} & t_{23} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.3)$$

where constants t_{ij} control the mixing between generations i and j .

4 Minimizing the Potential

To find the VEVs $\langle\phi_i\rangle$, we need to minimize the potential $V(\phi)$.

4.1 Calculating the Derivatives

The derivative of V with respect to $\phi_i^\dagger$ is set to zero:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial \phi_i^\dagger} = 0. \quad (4.1)$$

4.2 Computing the Derivatives

Each term contributes as follows:

Quadratic term:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi_i^\dagger} (-\mu^2 \phi^\dagger \phi) = -\mu^2 \phi_i. \quad (4.2)$$

Quartic term:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi_i^\dagger} (\lambda (\phi^\dagger \phi)^2) = 2\lambda (\phi^\dagger \phi) \phi_i. \quad (4.3)$$

Mixing term:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi_i^\dagger} (\alpha \phi^\dagger T \phi) = \alpha (T \phi)_i. \quad (4.4)$$

4.3 Setting the Derivatives to Zero

Combining these results, the equations become:

$$-\mu^2 \phi_i + 2\lambda (\phi^\dagger \phi) \phi_i + \alpha (T \phi)_i = 0, \quad (4.5)$$

which must hold for each component $i = 1, 2, 3$.

5 Finding Solutions

Solving these equations requires finding the values of v_i that satisfy all three simultaneously.

5.1 Case 1: No Mixing Between Generations

First, consider the simplest case where there is no mixing between generations, i.e., $T_{ij} = 0$ for all $i \neq j$.

5.1.1 Equations Simplify To

$$-\mu^2 v_i + 2\lambda V v_i = 0. \quad (5.1)$$

This equation is satisfied if either:

- $v_i = 0$, or
- $-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V = 0$.

5.1.2 Non-Trivial Solution

Assuming at least one $v_i \neq 0$, the condition $-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V = 0$ gives:

$$V = \frac{\mu^2}{2\lambda}. \quad (5.2)$$

This implies:

$$v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2 = \frac{\mu^2}{2\lambda}. \quad (5.3)$$

The VEVs v_i can be any set of real numbers satisfying this equation.

5.1.3 Multiple Solutions

There are infinitely many solutions corresponding to different choices of v_i , leading to different mass spectra.

5.2 Case 2: Including Mixing Between Generations

Now consider the general case with non-zero mixing terms T_{ij} .

5.2.1 Strategy

We need to solve the coupled equations, which can be written in matrix form.

5.2.2 Matrix Form

Define the vector $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, v_3)^T$. The equations become:

$$(-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V) \mathbf{v} + \alpha T \mathbf{v} = 0. \quad (5.4)$$

5.2.3 Combining Terms

$$(-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V) I \mathbf{v} + \alpha T \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (5.5)$$

where I is the identity matrix.

5.2.4 Eigenvalue Problem

Rewriting:

$$(\alpha T + (-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V) I) \mathbf{v} = 0. \quad (5.6)$$

This is an eigenvalue problem:

$$M \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (5.7)$$

where

$$M = \alpha T + (-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V) I. \quad (5.8)$$

5.2.5 Non-Trivial Solutions

Non-trivial solutions for $\mathbf{v}$ exist if the determinant of M is zero:

$$\det(M) = 0. \quad (5.9)$$

5.3 Solving the Determinant Equation

5.3.1 Determinant of M

Compute $\det(M)$ using the specific form of T and set it to zero.

5.3.2 Simplifying Assumptions

To make the problem tractable, let's make simplifying assumptions:

- Let $t_{12} = t_{23} = t_{13} = t$.
- Let $\alpha t = \epsilon$, which measures the mixing strength.

Then T and M become:

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & t & t \\ t & 0 & t \\ t & t & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.10)$$

$$M = (-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V) I + \epsilon \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.11)$$

5.3.3 Eigenvalues of M

The characteristic equation is:

$$\det(M) = 0. \quad (5.12)$$

Computing the eigenvalues λ_M of M yields:

$$|M - \lambda_M I| = 0. \quad (5.13)$$

5.3.4 Solving for Eigenvalues

Set:

$$M - \lambda_M I = (-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V - \lambda_M) I + \epsilon T. \quad (5.14)$$

The eigenvalues λ_M satisfy:

$$\det((-\mu^2 + 2\lambda V - \lambda_M) I + \epsilon T) = 0. \quad (5.15)$$

Solving this equation provides values for λ_M as functions of V .

5.3.5 Finding VEVs

Once λ_M is known, the eigenvectors $\mathbf{v}$ can be found. The VEVs v_i correspond to the components of these eigenvectors.

6 Interpretation of Solutions

The multiple solutions for V correspond to distinct VEV patterns, yielding different mass hierarchies across generations. Each v_i contributes a mass:

$$m_i^2 = 2\lambda v_i^2. \quad (6.1)$$

7 Specific Parameter Solution

7.1 Parameter Values

To illustrate, we set the parameters:

$$\mu^2 = 1, \quad \lambda = 1, \quad \epsilon = 0.1, \quad (7.1)$$

where $\epsilon = \alpha t$ represents small mixing.

7.2 Simplified Equations with Parameters

With these values, the equations simplify to:

$$(-1 + 2V)v_i + 0.1 \sum_{j \neq i} v_j = 0. \quad (7.2)$$

7.2.1 Summing Equations

Summing over i :

$$\sum_i (-1 + 2V)v_i + 0.1 \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} v_j = 0, \quad (7.3)$$

which simplifies to:

$$(-1 + 2V)(v_1 + v_2 + v_3) + 0.1 \times 2(v_1 + v_2 + v_3) = 0. \quad (7.4)$$

Since this equation simplifies to zero, we proceed by solving the original system.

7.3 Approximated Solutions

7.3.1 Leading Order Solution (Neglecting Mixing Term)

First, we neglect the mixing term:

$$(-1 + 2V)v_i \approx 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad V = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (7.5)$$

Then, the v_i values satisfy:

$$v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2 = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (7.6)$$

7.3.2 Including Mixing as Perturbation

When mixing is reintroduced:

$$0.1 \sum_{j \neq i} v_j = 0. \quad (7.7)$$

With 0.1 as a small parameter, the sum over v_j suggests approximately equal VEVs.

7.3.3 Possible Symmetric Solution

Assuming symmetric VEVs:

$$v_1 = v_2 = v_3 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \approx 0.408. \quad (7.8)$$

Verification:

$$(-1 + 2 \times \frac{1}{2})v_i + 0.1(v_j + v_k) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad 0 + 0.1(2 \times 0.408) \approx 0.0816, \quad (7.9)$$

indicating symmetric VEVs are approximate solutions under small mixing.

8 Interpretation of Solutions

8.1 Multiple Solutions

Multiple solutions for V correspond to distinct VEV patterns, yielding different mass hierarchies across generations. Each v_i contributes a mass:

$$m_i^2 = 2\lambda v_i^2. \quad (8.1)$$

9 Example Solution

9.1 Numerical Solution with Parameters

Setting $\mu^2 = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, and $\alpha t = 0.1$, we numerically solve Eq. (7.2) for approximate VEV values.

9.2 Symmetric Case

A symmetric choice of VEVs, $v_1 = v_2 = v_3$, satisfies:

$$v_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}, \quad (9.1)$$

producing a uniform mass hierarchy as a simple example.

10 Key Results and Implications

- **Scalar Field Components:** Three components yield three generations.
- **Symmetry Breaking and Mixing:** Potential and mixing terms yield diverse VEVs and mass hierarchies.
- **Non-Trivial Mass Hierarchies:** Solutions demonstrate possible mass differentiation, consistent with generation structure.

11 Conclusion

This model provides a theoretical framework that incorporates a scalar field with three components, introducing mass hierarchies through symmetry-breaking mechanisms. Future extensions could incorporate gauge fields and Yukawa couplings to align more closely with the Standard Model and observational data. By building on previous work, this study presents a step toward understanding particle generation.

References

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